

1 **Glycoprotein-based vulnerability in the circulating tumor cell.**

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6 We used next generation sequencing technologies to measure total transcription in circulating tumor cells
7 (CTC) obtained from the blood of women with stage IV breast cancer. We describe here activation of three
8 glycoproteins or glycoprotein-type genes in the CTC in human breast cancer. Glycoprotein pathway
9 targets selected by the tumor for dissemination included *HAS3*, *SPOCK1*, and *PRG2*.

10 Citations

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